

Municipal Solid Waste Management

(Composting and Vermicomposting)

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ABSTRACT

Composting has proved an effective way for municipalities to reduce both space and methane gas in landfills. Through years of research and trial and error the best methods for municipal solid waste composting are better understood. With a firm understanding of the microbial processes that take place during composting, the parameters for achieving a quality product can be controlled by physical means. A literature review was performed to outline the background, microbial processes, methodologies, environmental/health concerns, case studies, and the regulation behind the composting of municipal solid waste for both Eastern and Western countries.

1.0 Background

It is well known that the organic fractions of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) contribute to the production of methane in landfills [Lou & Nair, 2009; Lechner et al., 2002]. Thereby, destabilizing the organic fractions of MSW prior to landfilling can significantly reduce the amount of methane gas produced in a landfill [De Gioannis et al., 2009]. Furthermore, by composting and diverting the organic fraction from the MSW altogether can reduce methane emissions, save valuable landfill space and be sold as a high quality fertilizer [Lou & Nair, 2009; de Bertoldi et al., 1983]. In some instances methane gas is captured from a landfill and used as a fuel source. However, this process is not 100% efficient and not cost effective in certain scenarios [Lechner et al., 2002]. Included herein, is review of the processes involved in the composting of MSW.

2.0 Microbial Processes

Microbial processes have many applications within the field of environmental engineering including activated sludge systems, bioremediation, anaerobic digestion, and composting. Therefore, to better understand the composting process one must have some fundamental knowledge of microbiology. Microorganisms are classified by three domains which include Bacteria, Archaea, and Eukarya. Archaea include methanogens which are applicable in anaerobic digestion [Metcalf & Eddy, 2004]. With regards to composting, the focus will be on Bacteria. However, Eukarya include fungi and yeasts, are also present [Hassen et al., 2001; McCart & Rittman, 2001]. The essentials for bacterial growth include an electron donor or energy source (food), a Carbon and Nitrogen source, a terminal electron acceptor (TEA), and micronutrients. The empirical formula for a single bacterial cell is $C_5H_7O_2N$. They are

comprised of 75% water and 25% dry mass. 90% of the dry mass is organic and of this approximately 55% is carbon, 25% Oxygen, 7% Hydrogen, and 13% Nitrogen. The micronutrients required for cell growth include: Cu, Ni, Mo, Fe, Mg, Zn, and Na. Phosphorus (P) is also a requirement and often excluded from the empirical formula listed above and is rather implied that 2% of bacterial cells are P. The carbon source is usually provided by the electron donor if it is organic (heterotrophs) or can be obtained from inorganic sources such as CO₂ (autotrophs). The nitrogen source is provided by ammonium, nitrate, nitrite, and sometimes N₂. Bacteria can use various TEA's depending on species and availability and will usually select for the one that is more energetically favorable. Selecting for the most energetically favorable TEA allows for a greater fraction of the energy to be directed into cells synthesis which in turn leads to higher growth yields [McCarty & Rittman, 2001]. In anaerobic (absence of oxygen) environments, the electron donor and other inorganic compounds are used as the TEA, as a consequence, methane, foul odors and lower growth yields are produced [McCarty & Rittman, 2001; Leton & Stentiford, 1990]. Therefore, aerobic (presence of oxygen) environments where molecular oxygen is the most energetically favorable TEA, give higher growth yields and are desired for composting [McCarty & Rittman, 2001; Diaz et al., 2007].

3.0 Prime Conditions

Bacteria can grow under a wide range of environmental conditions. Once the prime conditions for growth are known, engineers can grow and select for desired conditions and yields by controlling the surrounding ambient conditions accordingly [de Bertoldi et al., 1983; McCarty & Rittman, 2001]. However, the composting process is dynamic and the factors for bacterial growth have many variables that are sometimes functions of each other [Lenton & Stentiford,

1990]. A literature review was performed to identify these key factors which are outlined below.

3.1 Temperature

Temperature plays an important role in microbial growth. Varying species grow and thrive under different temperature ranges. Under their respective temperature ranges there is an optimal temperature conducive to max growth [McCarty & Rittman, 2001]. It is well known that bacteria give off heat when they respire, or transfer their electrons to the TEA (O_2) [Finstien & Morris, 1975; de Bertoldi et al., 1983]. During the initial stages of composting process, the temperature is subsequently raised and the varying classes and species will rise and fall accordingly [Wainwright, 1999; Finstein & Morris, 1975]. As composting proceeds, the temperature declines as available substrates are utilized and microbial growth decreases [Finstien & Morris, 1975]. It is said that the prime temperature for composting occurs within the thermophilic range of 50 to 60 °C [Epstein, 1997; McCarty & Rittman, 2001]. The temperature can be controlled by indirect means used to control other factors for growth which will be discussed further [de Bertoldi, 1983].

3.2 pH

pH plays another role in microbial growth. Different species of bacteria grow and thrive at varying ranges of pH. Just like temperature, there is an optimum pH within their respective ranges [McCarty & Rittman, 2001].

During the composting process the pH is said to decrease and then increase as time progresses [Finstien & Morris, 1975]. The pH fluctuations seem to have a correlation with bacterial growth due to the formation of organic acids followed by the production of ammonia

[de Bertoldi et al., 1983]. However, the pH is harder to control and is rather considered unnecessary [Finstien, Morris, 1975].

3.3 Nutrients

If any one of the requirements for cell growth is unavailable then cell growth will be limited by that constituent [McCarty & Rittman, 2001]. The literature states that around 25 to 30 parts Carbon for 1 part Nitrogen (N) is desired for composting [de Bertoldi et al., 1983; Wainwright, 1999]. If this ratio is too high then the cells grow too fast and die off because they utilize all available N [Wainwright, 1999; Epstein, 1997; de Bertoldi et al., 1983]. If the ratio is too low then N is lost in the form of ammonia gas which produces foul odors and the resulting lower N content decreases the overall value of the finished compost and also limits cellular growth [Finstien & Morris, 1975; Wainwright, 1999]. The Proper C/N ratios can be obtained by incorporating the compost with other compostable ingredients (i.e. grass, wastewater sludge/biosolids) [Beyea et al., 1994; Richard, 1992].

3.4 Moisture

Moisture is another important parameter for composting. Bacteria require an aqueous phase in order to readily transfer electron carriers, nutrients and enzymes across their cell membrane [Willey et al. 2008]. If water is limited, the cells will become dehydrated and die [Wainwright, 1999]. Literature states that the moisture content of the compost should be in the range of 50 to 60% [Richard, 1992]. The moisture content of the compost is also a function of other variables. Water is a byproduct of microbial respiration, so moisture content will vary as a function of cell growth [Finstien & Morris, 1975]. On the other hand, water will be lost due to evaporation and aeration of the compost [Lenton & Stentiford, 1990]. Proper moisture can also

be obtained through the incorporation of wastewater sludge/biosolids or yard trimmings [de Bertoldi et al., 1983; Richard, 1992; Finstein & Morris, 1975].

3.5 Particle Size/Aeration

The particle size of the compost is another important consideration in the composting process. Bacteria attach themselves to the aqueous film on the surface of the substrate. Mathematically, it can be proven that as the particle size decreases, the overall available surface area increases. What this means is that, in theory, the smaller the particle, the greater the compost will be readily degraded. However, there is a trade off because as the particle size decreases so does the pore size [de Bertoldi et al., 1983]. The presence of water within the smaller pore spaces forms capillary fringes between the particles which block the flow of oxygen into the compost [Epstein, 1997; Richard, 1992]. If oxygen transfer is limited within the compost then anaerobic conditions take over and offset the added benefit of the increased surface area [Epstein, 1997; Richard, 1992]. The literature states the optimum particle size for composting can vary in the range of 1.3 to 7.6 cm depending on which type of aeration method used [Richard, 1992]. Some composting facilities will even mix the compost with wood chips to increase the free air space [Beyea et al., 1994].

4.0 Physical Processes for Composting in the United States

The organic matter naturally degrades in the environment due to microbial activity. Theoretically, this means that the compost will degrade naturally with no help from anthropogenic sources. However, this process takes a long time and produces foul odors [Wainwright, 1999; Bertoldi et al., 1983]. Therefore, engineering controls can be used to speed up the process and alleviate unwanted odors. The extent to which these engineering controls are

implemented would depend on a number of variables such as: infrastructure (available technology), composition of the composted waste, economics, municipality population (waste volume), and government regulations [Richard, 1992; Epstein, 1997; Diaz et al., 2007]. For example, the engineering controls used for composting might be different in India than what is done in the United States. The basic principles are the same, but different methods would be used when certain variables prevail.

After the EPA passed the Hazardous and Solid Waste Amendments (HSWA) in 1984, requiring that landfills “be state of the art,” and forcing municipalities to take an “integrated” approach to deal with MSW, did composting on a large scale become a necessity [Beyea et al., 1994; LeGrega, 2001; Harrison & Richard, 1992]. The recyclable and organic fractions of the MSW are now often treated as a valuable resource rather than a waste [Federal Register, 2008]. Depending on the nature of the MSW, a certain degree of separation, mixing, and size reduction is necessary before composting can begin [Richard, 1992]. A number of methods can be used and are listed herein.

4.1 Methods

4.1.1 Source Separated

This method relies on residents to separate organics from nonorganics through placement in different bins or containers for collection. Source separation has some advantages and disadvantages. One disadvantage is that not all residents actively participate in this collection method leading to a reduced volume of compost [Beyea et al., 1994]. Municipalities adopting this method should be aware that the volume of compostibles might be less than predicted, which can be detrimental to the design of composting facility [Richard, 1992]. Another disadvantage is that collection is costly [Beyea et al., 1994]. An advantage to source separation is that the

quality of the composted end product is higher [Beyea et al., 1994; Richard, 1992]. Furthermore, this separation method might be more amenable to certain municipalities where public involvement is greater [Beyea et al., 1994].

4.1.2 Centralized Separation

The other method for separating organics is through mechanical and physical means at the landfill. The organic fraction is comingled and collected along with the MSW and therefore must be separated. Advantages to this method are that it allows for a greater volume of recovery of compostable material and that added collection expenses for the recovery of recyclables are avoided because they can be collected and separated with the comingled MSW [Beyea et al., 1994]. A disadvantage to this method is that the quality of the compost can be jeopardized [Beyea et al., 1994; Richard, 1992]. Municipalities using centralized separation must take added measures to ensure that contaminant levels in the end product lie below EPA standards [Richard, 1992; Epstein, 1997]. There are a number of methods used to separate comingled MSW based on different physical properties [Richard, 1992].

The first is the age old technology of manpower. Even the most advanced technology sometimes has its limitations. At the tipping floor, workers can begin to separate potential contaminants, heavy, and obvious noncompostable materials, which would otherwise cause damage or impede further separation technologies down the line. Of course, health concerns are an issue here and all the necessary precautions should be taken to ensure personnel safety such as the use of personal protective equipment and proper ventilation [Richard, 1992].

The second separation method is the use of screens. This method allows the MSW to be separated according to size. A common problem associated with screens is clogging; therefore, screens are often designed accordingly. One type of screen is the stationary vibrating screen.

The screens vibrate and are slightly sloped, which causes larger items to be either shaken or rolled off the screen. Another type of screen is the trommel screen, which according to the literature; seem to be the preferred method of screening. These screens are rotating drums that are also slightly sloped, allowing larger items to pass through the screen. A brush is used to prevent clogging [Richard, 1992].

Another separation method is magnetic separation. The screened material can be transported on a conveyer where the use of magnets is employed to separate out ferrous metals. This method of separation is cheap but will not separate nonferrous metals such as copper or aluminum. For these metals an eddy current separator is used. Here, repulsive force is applied to the metals that are able to conduct electricity and should only be used after magnetic separation [Richard, 1992].

Air classification and wet separation are other methods. In air classification, the waste stream is fed into a housing unit where a large air stream is applied. The lighter materials are carried along with the air stream, while the heavier items drop down and out of the stream flow. In wet separation, the waste stream is placed in water where the lighter organic fractions float and are scraped of the top while denser materials sink to the bottom [Richard, 1992]. This type of separation is useful for the separation of glass [Beyea et al., 1994].

Ballistics separation is another useful separation technology. Here, the waste stream is dropped onto a rotating drum and thrown forward and is thus separated by its resulting trajectory. Heavier, more elastic inorganic materials are thrown farthest and while the lighter, less elastic organic materials consequently have the shortest trajectory [Beyea et al., 1994; Richard, 1992].

4.1.3 Size Reduction/Mixing

As mentioned earlier, particle size is an important factor in the composting process. Various similar engineering technologies can be used to achieve the optimal particle size. Size reduction can be employed either before or after separation. In some of the above separation technologies, size reduction prior to separation will increase the removal efficiency. The incorporation of wood chips, yard trimmings or biosolids from the municipal wastewater treatment plant, to correct for nutrient, moisture, and aeration deficiencies, could simultaneously be done with size reduction. The predominant technologies employed for size reduction are hammermills, rotating drums, and shear shredders. The selection of any one technology will likely be based on performance and power requirements. The extent of mixing will likely be based on laboratory testing of the compost [Richard, 1992].

4.2 Processes Controls

Once the optimum physical conditions of the compost are achieved, the process controls can be implemented. The two common types of systems used in composting MSW are aerated static piles and turned windrows. The basic construction of the two systems is the same [Richard, 1992]. The compost is piled in long rows approximately 2.5 meters high to 6 meters wide but can vary depending on weather conditions [Beyea et al., 1994; Diaz et al., 2007; Richard, 1992]. However, the difference lies in the way aeration is achieved [Beyea et al., 1994; Diaz et al., 2007].

4.2.1 Turned Windrow

In a turned windrow system, the piles are aerated by mechanically turning the compost. This system relies on the molecular diffusion of oxygen for aeration. However, since molecular diffusion cannot reach the inner most reaches, the pile must be periodically turned [Richard,

1992]. When the piles are turned the inner part is transferred to the outer part and vice versa [Beyea et al., 1994]. This ensures that the pile is composted evenly and that anaerobic conditions and thus unwanted odors do not form [Beyea et al., 1994; Diaz et al., 2007]. As described earlier, the temperature and moisture are important parameters in composting [Finstein & Morris, 1975]. When the piles are turned the temperature and moisture are subsequently lowered [Lenton & Stentiford, 1990]. However, if moisture is lacking, the piles can be watered while being turned [Richard, 1992; Beyea et al., 1994]. According to EPA standards, temperatures must reach 55° C for 72 hours within the pile to kill any pathogens present [Beyea et al., 1994; Richard, 1992; Epstein, 1997; Wainwright, 1999]. However, since temperatures are usually higher in the inner most pile due to the effects of insulation, proper turning must take place to ensure that all the compost reaches the required temperature level [Epstein, 1997]. Turning can be achieved by the use of specialized machinery or conventional front end loaders [Richard, 1992; Diaz et al., 2007]. Generally speaking, the more frequently the piles are turned the faster the rate of composting [Diaz et al., 2007; Beyea et al., 1994].

4.2.2 Aerated Static Piles

In aerated static piles, turning is not required because aeration is achieved through the use of blowers. The blowers are used to either force air up through the pile or to suck air down through the pile [Lenton & Stentiford, 1990; Diaz et al., 2007]. The advantage of sucking the air down through the pile is that the air can be treated for odors. Since blowers are used, piping and screens must be constructed under the area which the piles are placed. The forced air subsequently cools the pile and thus the temperature can be controlled in this manner. Literature states that a continuous flow of air is not necessary and that the aeration could be automated with temperature levels [Lenton & Stentiford, 1990; Diaz et al., 2007]. Generally speaking,

composting rates are considered to be greater for the aerated static pile than for the turned windrow [Richard, 1992].

4.2.3 Curing

After the compost is stabilized or all available substrates are used and microbial growth ceases. The compost is cured to ensure any remaining nutrients and microorganisms are gone. The compost piles are reconstructed into smaller piles and no process controls are used. If the temperature of the new piles is raised, then it is an indication that the composting process is not finished. The compost is cured for approximately one month and the finished product should not give off any foul odors. Literature states that the final C/N ratio should be around 20/1 [Beyea et al., 1994].

5.0. Composting and Vermicomposting in Countries other than US.

Composting and Vermicomposting are processes practiced on large as well as small scale in most of the Asian countries. Some of the companies have come forward to setup large vermicomposting plants for treatment of food waste generated by restaurants and dwellers in their vicinity. According to recent data available, India generates almost 25M tones of solid waste per annum, which is of a diverse composition. Also the per capita generation of waste estimates to 0.4kg/day. This waste has approximately 50-60% of compostable matter. But mostly this waste matter is dumped leading to soil and water pollution. Hence bio-techniques like vermicomposting or commonly called as earthworm farming used for conversion of solid organic waste into compost for horticulture have come forward.[Asha Alok et.al., 2008]

Vermicomposting is one of the predominant techniques in countries like Japan, Italy, India and China. Ontario (Canada) was the first to implement this technology in 1970. It

processes about 75 tonnes of refuse per week in recent years. Aoka Sangyo Co. Ltd., Japan has about 3 plants having capacity of 1000 tones/month. Vermicomposting has also been practiced on a large scale in Italy and Philippines commercially. [Palaniappan et.at. 2005]

6.0. Measurement of Parameters

Generally the parameters like moisture content, temperature, pH, organic content, C/N ratio are all important for a good quality compost as a final product. These all parameters should be well maintained and should be measured on a regular basis. A slight variation in these parameters will not affect the compost yard that drastically but for vermicomposting, these parameters if not maintained may prove fatal for earthworms.

6.1. Moisture Content

Moisture Content is one of the critical factors in composting process. Earthworms usually breathe through their skin. Thus the compost is required to be moist at all the times. But too much moisture also can be a disadvantage for compost. The moisture content in thermophilic composting normally is about 45-60% and equally for vermi-composting. [Edwards and Lofty,1996]. Moisture content above this limit makes the compost too wet and thus turns it into anaerobic as the oxygen content in water is far lower than that in air. The moisture content in the compost can be calculated by formula

$$\frac{\text{Weight of wet sample} - \text{Weight of dry sample}}{\text{Weight of wet sample}} \times 100$$

6.2. Organic Content

The organic content is also an important factor during composting process. The change in organic content of the compost material is found using a muffle furnace. The muffle furnace at 600oC burns away all the organic matter leaving all the inorganic matter behind. The difference between the weights of the matter taken on a percentage scale gives the total organic content initially present.[Wani 2002].

6.3. pH

Measurement and maintaining pH is important in composting. It is the measure of active acidity of the compost. The range of pH for the compost material is generally between 5.5 and 8.0. a neutral pH is suitable or desired for finished compost. pH is generally measure using the pH measurement strips which come in different colours. A small amount of compost material is generally added to almost 100 ml of water in a beaker and a few drops of pH solution are added to it. The change in colour is observed and the colour is compared to the pH strip to determine the pH of the compost.

Figure 1 : pH strips used to determine pH

6.4. Temperature

Temperature plays an important role in survival of the worms in vermi-composting, though it doesn't matter much in thermophilic composting. The worms *Eisenia Foetida* generally survive in the temperature range of 20oC to 30oC. But the maximum performance by these worms is obtained at 25oC.[Reinecke et al. 1992] the temperature can be directly measured by inserting the thermometer in the compost.

7.0. Vermicomposting

Vermiculture Biotechnology is an innovative discipline which usually deals with the proliferation and propagation of the worms, using the earthworm castings for manure is now an important tool in the field of waste recycling all over the world. These earthworms act as bioreactors for economical and environmentally resonant waste management. The nutrients need of most of the agricultural sector can be fulfilled by the vermiculture to a great extent and also result in growth in employment and growth and development of rural areas as a faster rate. [Asha et.al. 2008]

The earthworms used in the vermicomposting break-down the organic waste on soil surface was first highlighted by Darwin in 1881. But it has taken almost a hundred years for environmentalist to appreciate the importance in curbing the organic pollution, thus providing a good quality soil to impecunious lands.[kale, 1998]

The actual vermi-composts are very finely divided materials. These have high porosity, high ventilation and also drainage and water withholding capacity. There is a microbial activity stabilization occurring due to the interaction between the earthworms and micro-organisms

[Edwards and Burrows, 1988]. All the 16 essential nutrients like phosphates, nitrates, soluble potassium, and exchangeable calcium etc. required by the plants are supplied by vermicomposting [Orozco et.al. 1996]. Large particulate area of vermicompost proves helpful for microbial activity and also in withholding the nutrients [Fu-Zhen et.al 1991].

Vermicomposting can be either done in pits or also in tanks build above the ground surface using materials like concrete, fiber, wood or plastic depending upon various factors. Generally a shade is required above the vermi-compost to avoid interference of direct sunlight. Also it is recommended that the site is located in an upland so as to avoid the water stagnation during the rainy season. Going through the normal procedure of vermi-composting, it takes approximately 45 days for the compost to be ready. The compost when ready is spongy in nature, smells sweet and also dark brown in color. [Ismail, 1997]

7.1. Precautions during Vermicomposting

There are a lot of precautions to be followed while practicing vermi-composting in order for the worms to survive and also to obtain good quality manure. There is a need to maintain proper moisture content during the process. A dry compost results in death of worms and stagnant conditions also kill the worms due to lack of oxygen. While preparing the compost it is necessary that plant based materials should be used for eg leaves, dry grass, bagasse (dry sugarcane) etc. A shed is required for interference of sunlight and rain and also for protection from birds and pet animals. The compost should also be protected from ants and termites. The measurement of parameters shall be done at regular intervals. The earthworms to be used for vermi-composting shall be used taken into consideration the nature of compost.[Wani, et.al., 2004]

7.2. Advantages of Vermicompost

The castings of the worms or technically called vermi-compost have been analyzed for its chemical and biological factors and properties. The castings when compared to the thermophilic compost has been found to be richer in containing micro and macro nutrients required by the plants.[Jadhav et.al 1997] The application of vermi-composts results in higher germination thus improving the yield of different plants.[Karmegam, et.al., 1998] The earthworms also play an worthy role in recycling Nitrogen in shift cultivation. [bahaduria 1996]. Cotton waste and cattle manure when mixed in proportion of 1:5 give best results for multiplication of earthworms.[Sidor 1990]. Earthworms also facilitate the prevention of loss of nutrients during decomposition.

8. Case Study

The Barnes Nursery, Inc. is composting firm situated in Huron, Ohio which has been working since 1992. This is privately owned company and open for public. This facility collects about 20,000 tons of waste from which about 8500 tons are yard waste, 500 to 1000 tons of food residuals, and others are wood and aggregate. Composting facility is using windrow method as shown in figure 2 [Christensen et al., 2009] to manage the waste. The waste is basically collected on conveyor belt and bucket loaders and separated through screens. The area of site is about 35 acres from which about 20 acres are used as composting facility. There are 4 full time employee and 3 are part time employee working at this facility. The finished products are sold at their retail stores. The main sources of these wastes are from restaurants, resorts, hospitals, grocery stores, hotels, schools, food market, etc. This facility is class two composting facility, so they need to fulfill the requirement for that. This facility needs to be register with the state and take license to

run this facility. They need to keep record of every waste which collected from different sites. They collect all wastes in their own trucks but they are not able to collect all food residual due to limit of weight of Ohio roads [Christensen et al., 2009]. The collection method also depends on individual source of generator. From above generators mainly 30% source is vegetables and meats, 70% cardboard and other boxes. They also collect the waste from nearby cities which includes 75% back garden waste, 15% paper and about 10% of food residuals. In this facility they have created separate arrangement to collect and process food residual from other waste. All food residuals are spread on ground which contains 12 to 20 inch of yard waste to reduce the moisture content. To control odor problem in this facility, they cover the waste by spreading it on windrow with shredded yard waste as soon as they arrive, as for outdoor facility odor and animals are major problems. To generate good compost, they do not put too much bulking on a pile with more than 75% of card board as that waste dries out early and slow down the rate of compost. On other hand they mix little bulk with card board to reduce the amount of free water [Christensen et al., 2009].

For successful future, this facility suggested to charge 5\$ per ton as tipping fees from county landfill facility as they divert their waste. The county landfill facility had also been supportive about this suggestion as they want to encourage the reduction program [Christensen et al., 2009].

Figure 2. Windrows at Barnes Nursery

9. Environmental, health and safety concerns

Composting organic materials are very beneficial to the land. They add nutrients into the soil and decrease the water contamination. To protect environment, the design plan of composting site takes major role. If the composting process is not done carefully, it could create many environmental issues like air pollution, water pollution, odor, noise, fires [Beyea et al., 1994].

9.1. Water Pollution

Leachate, runoff and ponding are main concern of water pollution by composting process. Leachate runs downward and absorb by composite pile and this leachate can pollute the ground water. Due to precipitation on landfill runoff occurs and this also creates erosion. Both leachate and runoff create pond around the landfill which causes odor. Cure should be taken against leachate, runoff and ponding [Beyea et al., 1994].

9.1.1. Leachate

Leachate from agricultural composting site contains high amount of BOD, ammonia and phenol compounds. This BOD when mixes with lake or river water, it reduces the oxygen contain. This is harmful to fish and other aquatic animals. Another major contaminant of composite site is nitrate compound. This compound is generated by composition of leaves as it has higher C: N ratio. Leachate produced from composting also contains some amount of toxic synthetic. Production of Leachate can be controlled by monitoring the moisture level in the composting pile. To reduce the moisture level, pile can be set under the roof. In the initial stage leachate from composting creates itself without adding any moisture but as product gets older, amount of leachate decreases. If moisture contain is above the limit then that leachate is transported to waste water treatment plant if they accept it [Decision Maker's Guide to Solid

Waste Management, Volume II, (EPA 530-R-95-023), 1995; Beyea et al., 1994]. If facility finds high amount of contaminant in the leachate, they will treat it in onsite waste water treatment plant [Beyea et al., 1994].

9.1.2. Run Off

Run off can be produced by heavy rainfall or by the composting process which uses water. When trucks from grocery store and restaurants are emptied on the composting site, it also releases some polluted water which contains small amount of metal, pesticides and inorganic compounds. If runoff contains solids, then preventing measures like screening, settling and skimming should be taken [Beyea et al., 1994].

10.1.3. Ponding

Run on or ponding is another problem with the composting site. To prevent site from ponding slight slope should be built [Beyea et al., 1994].

9.2. Air Pollution

Odor from composting site is most important problem but other than that air pollution is not major concern. Minor problems like dust emission from vehicular movement and in summer dust can be generated from dry, uncontrolled organic particles released from screening and shredding operations. This air pollution could not be a problem as long as buffer zone around site is as per regulation [Beyea et al., 1994].

9.2.1. Odor

Odor is very serious problem in all MSW composting plant which even caused the shutdown of many composting facility. Wind direction consideration in selecting composting site takes main role. Prevention and control measures should be taken while planning and designing

the facility. After taking these measures, if odor still occurs then facility need to take actions like discover the source, intensity, frequency and characteristics of odor. Odorous compounds like dimethyl disulfide, ammonia, hydrogen sulfide, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, etc. are the sources [Kissel et al., 1992; Beyea et al., 1994]. Odor can be produced during many composting operation like mixing, curing, conveying and storage [Kissel et al., 1992; Beyea et al., 1994]. Many operations are used to control odor based on source, intensity and characteristics of odor. Odor can be controlled by facility while composting process is running. If the waste is already in odorous form then facility should mix it with wood chips to minimize its effect [Richard, 1992; Beyea et al., 1994]. Many other criteria such as size of piles to infiltrate the oxygen, flipping the piles to reduce the wetness, breaking the piles to dry and to cover pile under roofs for reducing odor effect. While planning the design of a composting facility many latest types of equipment are used to minimize the effect of odor. Combustion is very proficient but costly method. Biofilters and air scrubbers are getting popular now a day's [Beyea et al., 1994].

Various methods like odor pile, biofilter, wet scrubbers, adsorption, dispersion enhancement and combustion. In odor pile method, odorous gases are diverted from composting pile. In wet scrubbers, odorous compounds are mixed with liquid and then taken out with chemicals. Its effectiveness is about 70%. In adsorption method, various gases are passed over a medium and odorous compound attach with them. This method is effective in removal of volatile organic compounds. In combustion method, gases react with odorous compounds and then they are burned. Effectiveness of this method is about 99% [Beyea et al., 1994].

9.2.1.1. Biofilters

Biofilters are most commonly used to reduce the odor while composting. It consists of blowers which collect and transport gases to biofilter. Soil, wood chips, peat, sand or mixture of this can be used as filtration medium [Pagans et al., 2005; Decision Maker's Guide to Solid Waste Management, Volume II, (EPA 530-R-95-023), 1995; Beyea et al., 1994]. Fatigue air from composting materials contains moisture also, which effects on equipment and building as its corrosive in nature [Decision Maker's Guide to Solid Waste Management, Volume II, (EPA 530-R-95-023), 1995]. When gases are collected in biofilter, it is then evenly distributed on that medium. Pipes which transport the gases are surrounded by gravel. The efficiency of biofilters depends on air flow rate, dimension and type of filter medium and characteristics of gases. Additional nutrients are not needed to add in biofilter medium as it has enough nitrogen content and other organisms [Pagans et al., 2005]. There are mainly two types of biofilters are used: 1) Open biofilter System and 2) Closed biofilter System, as shown in below [Beyea et al., 1994].

Figure 3. Open and closed Biofilter System

9.3. Occupational Health Concern

Municipal solid waste contains many pathogens, toxic compounds and other micro organisms [Gillett, 1992]. Noise and safety issues with equipment should be considered as a major concern for workers [Beyea et al., 1994]. This can be eliminated by education safety training. Bioaerosols are caused due to composting; this micro organism can stay in air for long time, which effect on workers [Domingo, 2008; Beyea et al., 1994]. Aspergillus fungus is a pathogenic fungus which causes infection in nose, throat and other infectious area [Domingo, 2008]. Breathable mycotoxins cause cancer in workers. Aspergillus is a fungus that can enter in human body from cut of the skins [Beyea et al., 1994]. Exposure from organic dust also causes irritation in eyes and ears, fever, asthma, skin irritation and gastro [Domingo, 2008]. Pathogens can be divided into primary and secondary human pathogens.

Primary Human Pathogens

The generation of these pathogens is basically from baby and adult diapers and other house hold medical wastes [Epstein, 1997; Gillett, 1992]. Composting facility has same range and strength of primary human pathogens as waste water treatment plant. Many primary pathogens can be efficiently reduced by increasing the temperature. Many viruses and bacteria can be reduced by maintaining the temperature between 45°C to 60°C [Gillett, 1992].

Secondary Human Pathogens

Organisms like fungus, bacteria, arthropods and actinomycetes are basically known as Secondary human pathogens [Epstein, 1997; Gillett, 1992]. Symptoms of these pathogens are mainly runny nose, irritation in eyes, ear and skin, nausea. This happens due to organic dust in composting facility. This fungus grows in the temperature more than 45°C of putrefying the vegetables [Gillett, 1992].

Trace Metals

Trace metals are also termed as heavy metal which has high molecular weight. Zinc (Zn), Nickel (Ni), Cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), lead (Pb), mercury (Hg) and copper (Cu) are some of the heavy metals. Due to the use of fertilizer, pesticides, etc have increased the amount of trace metals in soils. To decrease the amount of heavy metals, wood chips and other bulking agents are added. The solubility of metals depends on the pH value. If pH value is more than 6.5, then solubility is high [Epstein, 1997].

Workers in composting facility should take some remedy measure against their health like wearing uniform and mask while working. Facility should provide shower, ventilations and shoe facilities at work place [Epstein, 1997; Gillett, 1992].

10.0. Economy of Composting Facility

Over the past 10 years composting facilities have been increased due to the advantages like reduction in volume of waste, uses of finished composting material. As it increase the life of landfill tipping fees could be avoided [Beyea et al., 1994]. The cost of constructing landfill facility is much more than the composting facility but it is not yet popular. On other hand, in metropolitan cities composting facility is highly encouraged. Cost of collection and transportation, labor cost, site preparation cost, operation and maintenance cost, equipment cost, fuel and marketing cost is greater for composting facility than landfill facility [Beyea et al., 1994]. Main disadvantage of this facility is that, they involve great cost in initial process like screening, separation and removal of materials from incoming waste. Composting can be run by basically three firms: 1) Privately owned and operated, 2) Publicly owned and operated and 3) Publicly owned but privately operated. Publicly owned facility handle small quantity of waste

[Renkow, 1998]. 19 facilities were surveyed by telephone interview to get economic budget. Out of which 3 facilities were closed due to odor problems and technology problems. In-vessel technology was more popular among these facilities. This composting materials primary used by farmers and remaining is used as landfill cover or roadside dirt filling. The selling cost is lower than the producing cost. Finished composting material also contains impurities like plastic and glass particles. These facilities provided the cost of composting materials per ton which does not include the cost of initial operations. The average cost of composting is \$55 per ton and selling price is lower than this price [Renkow, 1998]. In year 2000, 27.7 million ton of yard trimming was generated through municipal solid waste and out of that 15.8 million ton was recovered by composting facility and remaining was discarded. Like that they reduced 21.2 million ton of yard trimming each year. [Stutz et al., 2003]

11.0. Laws and Regulations

Laws and regulations are different for MSW composting and yard trimming composting. More states have accepted regulation for yard trimming composting than MSW composting [Beyea et al., 1994]. Composting facility has to take state permit before opening it. Still there are no federal laws and regulations are available for composting facility [Harrison & Richard, 1992; Epstein, 1997; Beyea et al., 1994]. Every state has different laws and regulation for designing and operating composting facility. For sitting of composting facility, they need to consider the environmental effect due to odor and other issues related with health on neighboring [Epstein, 1997]. To protect water quality various factors like depth of ground water table and aquifer depth should be considered [Harrison & Richard, 1992]. Facility also needs to design the odor control. Designed plan should describe the design of leachate collection, soil erosion, drainage system,

structures, waste storage area, site boundary, odor control, air and noise pollution control [Epstein, 1997; Beyea et al., 1994]. Buffer zone requirement (100 ft from property line, 500 ft from residential area, and 200 ft from water level) should be fulfilled by the facility [Epstein, 1997; Harrison & Richard, 1992]. Detailed design should be permitted by state environmental agency before constructing composting facility. The main reason of this legislation is to minimize the risk against environment and human. Many regulations are just based on the acceptance of incoming wastes. Many other countries like Europe, Canada, and British do not follow this regulation but they have created standards for finished compost which prevents them to allow some input waste [Harrison & Richard, 1992]. Batteries, cells, house hold hazardous wastes are also prohibited by state regulation from accepting them into facility. There are certain standards which composting facility has to maintain like highest contaminant level of heavy metals, toxic compounds, pathogen level and glass and plastic residuals [Harrison & Richard, 1992]. These standards also guide to maintain the minimum level of certain nutrient. Facility need to maintain standards for particle size. Different states have their own contaminant standards like Iowa State has no maximum contaminant level [Harrison & Richard, 1992]. States regulations do not apply for the incoming finished compost products [Harrison & Richard, 1992].

There are mainly three basic criteria to design the regulations: 1) No-net degradation, 2) Risk- based approach and 3) Best- achievable approach. No net degradation rules provide the information about the maximum level of heavy metals and contaminant in the soil. The main problem of this rule is that it is hard to maintain the level of contaminant on the land which uses fertilizer or pesticide or other chemicals. All European and Canadian countries facilities are based on this rule. Risk based approach rule consider the human and environmental effect due to the chemicals. EPA uses this rule to develop laws and regulations. Best achievable approach

ignores all the risks on human and environment due to the effect of toxic chemicals [Epstein, 1997; Harrison & Richard, 1992].

12.0. References

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